

IoT based Educational Companion for the visually Impaired

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Abstract—The project aims to create an educational companion system specifically designed to cater to the unique learning requirements of individuals with visual impairments. This proposed system harnesses existing technologies to establish an inclusive and interactive learning environment, promoting self-sufficiency and enriched educational experiences. The primary goal of this research is to develop a holistic solution that tackles the obstacles faced by visually impaired learners when it comes to accessing and comprehending educational materials, including textual content and non-textual elements such as shapes and other visual information that cannot be conveyed through text alone. This innovation would enable visually impaired individuals to independently read printed materials without relying on external assistance, thereby promoting full autonomy and eliminating the need for scribes and other support personnel in their educational journey.

Keywords: educational companion, visually impaired, visualizing geometry, text to speech.

Index Terms—component, formatting, style, styling, insert

I. INTRODUCTION

Visually impaired people face a lot of difficulties in their daily life. However, one of the biggest challenges comes in the matters of education. As most of us would agree, education is one of the most vital things for a person in our modern world. This value is tenfold when it comes to someone that is already struggling to catch up to the rest of society.

While society has done a lot to try and make sure that they can live their lives relatively comfortably, there is still a lot of work to be done. The base necessities like walking around and basic survival in our world are being considered. However, when it comes to education, the solutions are lacking behind severely. Solutions like audio books and braille exist, however, these solutions have their own issues. The main issue is that these solutions have to be manually created. Audio books have gained popularity recently, but they are not available for every

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book still, especially when it comes to textbooks where the content is harder to describe in audio. Braille on the other hand, is available for even less books as they appeal to a far smaller audience. Manual transcribers also exist, but they charge a heavy fee which might add to the burden of the visually impaired people, not to mention the additional reliance on other people.

Our solution attempts to allow visually impaired people a level of independence by being able to transcribe things quickly and efficiently. Once a prototype is made, it could be turned into a more large scale product that could help a number of visually impaired people with their education as well as save them a lot of money that they would have spent on alternate short term solutions.

Figure 1: Correlation between deafblindness and lower incomes

The statistics provided by The World Federation of the Deafblind show that blind people struggle significantly more in their economic status compared to people without these disabilities. This might seem natural but to build an inclusive society, it is important to uplift individuals to the point where they can be independent socioeconomically and one important step towards doing that is education.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The first literature review for the given abstract discusses the importance of Braille as a vital means of communication for the visually impaired. The abstract emphasizes that Braille is a critical tool for education and employment opportunities for blind individuals. It also introduces the concept of a "Text to Braille Conversion system" as a means to bridge the communication gap between those who do not know Braille and the visually impaired who do. The review discusses the significance of Braille as a means of communication for the blind and notes the slower reading rate for Braille readers compared to print readers. It highlights the importance of Braille in enhancing the quality of life for visually impaired individuals and the potential for making it more accessible through technology. The review mentions efforts to develop technology for converting text to Braille, such as direct-translation units and print recognition algorithms. It discusses the advantages and disadvantages of using Braille over voice synthesis and emphasizes the need for low-cost devices to convert Braille code into the alphabet to facilitate communication for visually impaired individuals. Additionally, the review introduces a prototype device that converts text to Braille using micro-controller-based technology, providing a practical solution to the communication gap. It explains the methodology of the device, which uses servo motors to create Braille impressions for each letter of the alphabet.

The problem statement outlines the objective of the Text to Braille Conversion System, which is to enable communication between individuals who do not know Braille and visually impaired individuals. The system's potential impact on employment and education prospects is emphasized. Overall, this literature review provides a comprehensive overview of the importance of Braille, the challenges faced by visually impaired individuals, and the potential of technology to bridge communication gaps. It sets the stage for the proposed Text to Braille Conversion System as a promising solution to these challenges.

The second paper introduces a significant innovation: A Voice Activated Braille system, designed as a portable device to empower individuals who are blind or visually impaired by enabling them to recognize written characters independently. This system is controlled by Arduino that plays a pivotal role in making this device both accessible and affordable. The primary objective is to serve as a guiding tool for the blind, creating a virtual environment. This innovation strives to reduce the existing communication gap and challenges faced by visually impaired individuals, particularly in countries with limited resources and high incidences of blindness. This paper also highlights a compelling need for affordable and efficient Braille technology, where blindness is a growing concern. The proposed Voice Activated Braille system seeks to address various challenges faced by blind people, providing them with greater autonomy and access to written information. At the core of this innovation are electromagnetic solenoids that effectively display Braille characters, allowing the blind to

read text with their fingertips. This design aims for portability and simplicity. The system receives voice commands through a Bluetooth connection, which are then translated into Braille characters displayed on the device. Additionally, audio feedback is provided to the user, enhancing the overall experience and usability.

The estimated cost and feasibility analysis of this Voice Activated Braille system demonstrate its potential to significantly improve communication and accessibility for visually impaired individuals. The paper underscores the importance of creating a practical, low-cost solution to empower those with visual impairments. It is notable that the proposed device is cost-effective in comparison to existing Braille technologies.

In this Paper they have mentioned three technologies that is the NIST rotating wheel braille reader concept is a rotate wheel that incorporates the braille text on the wheel's bottom, like a tyre roll. The braille dots at one stage of the rotation of the wheel is mounted by a limited number of actuators (three 6 dot-braille actuators, four 8 dot-braille actuators), which stay steady and simple to read over an expanded reading area to enable a read of several fingers. They also created a new tactile display control technology, called the Passive Pin Displacement System, to promote this writing mode and further minimize the costs of the braille display. In this new method, set, powerless sensors are used to control the points and their attached pins for much of the wheel rotation relative to the Braille points with the wheel rotation. Active monitoring is only implemented at a point at which the actuators fix the pin readings. This also includes a Dot Braille watch through which a visually impaired persons can read time through the 6 pin s in the watch . The paper also includes Orbit Reader 20 which is a device of 349 euros is a coalition of sight loss groups from around the globe led by RNIB, formed by Orbit Research and transforming Braille Community. The technical design and module design of the system reflect a deep understanding of the challenges encountered during development. The system's compactness, affordability, and focus on user convenience make it a promising tool for enhancing the communication and independence of visually impaired individuals. The paper concludes by mentioning the potential for future work, such as the integration of Deep Learning methodologies to further enhance voice activation predictability and system performance. This promising innovation holds the potential to positively impact the lives of visually impaired individuals, particularly in regions with limited resources and high incidences of blindness.

III. METHODOLOGY

The educational companion aims to help the user with reading and comprehending the content present in things like textbooks, research papers, question papers, etc. Two options are presented to the user, namely, the text to speech system and the braille board system. Together, this gives the user the choice to interpret content the way it is preferable for them and also by what is better for that specific piece of content that they are trying to understand. The major components of the

prototype would be a camera, a Raspberry Pi and a prototype braille board.

Figure 2: Block Diagram of Methodology

A. Text to speech module

The text to speech module works by using the camera to capture an image of the board, then using OCR technology to turn it into text. This text would then be run through a text to speech module and outputted to the user. The user can use earphones to listen to the audio output and listen to the contents of the page that they captured. The major challenge in making this would be to set the system up to make it easy for a visually impaired person to be able to use it, as they would not be able to have a proper understanding of how the page is being captured in the camera.

B. Braille Representation

The braille board module is what would help the user the most, by translating the book into a system that is widely used by visually impaired people to read. On top of this, this module is also what will help with diagrams and similar visual content that cannot be represented well in audio. The braille board is a board with many pins that would rise to give a tactile feedback, allowing us to simulate braille script and also make representations of diagrams and visual content.

The input system would work similar to the text to speech module, however, this time, it would split the paper into text and visual content. The text content will be represented as braille script by using a translation module. This would be converted into a 2x3 matrix of 1s and 0s. The 1 would be represent a rise in the board and the 0 would represent the pin staying down. By using this, we can replicate what it would be like to read from a braille script, one character at a time. This would then be fed to the board allowing the pins to be raised accordingly, thereby allowing the user to sense the character and perceive it.

The most challenging aspect of building the prototype would be the braille board itself. After looking at many similar solutions, we settled on using solenoids to move the pins on the board. The model we will be building would be a prototype, using a 2x3 grid.

C. Diagrammatic Representation

Diagrams are an aspect that are often difficult to deal with for visually impaired individuals, for this reason, we would

also be attempting to represent diagram on our braille board. This will be done by using the grid like pattern of the board to get a tactile feedback of the diagram.

The pins can be raised according to the input. So for a line, it can leave all the pins down, only raising those required to resemble a line. For a square, it can do the same thing but represent the edges of the square. It can do the same for more complex figures by following the same idea of raising pins where the ink should be and keeping the pins depressed for all the blank sections of the page. For example, we have taken the following diagram to be represented on the braille board.

Figure 3: The diagram to be converted, a simple square.

Now, this image will be run through the code to be converted into a binary matrix of 0s and 1s which should represent the diagram.

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0000000000
0000000000
0000111110
0000100010
0000100010
0000100010
0000111110
0000000000
0000000000
  
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Figure 3: The binary matrix representing the diagram.

This process is difficult, the main challenge being that for certain resolutions, it may not work as well. The biggest problem is curves, for example, a circle. At a smaller resolution, describing the edges may not be perfect. The method used divides the image into multiple sections, of the same resolution as the final binary matrix, and then for each section, decides whether it should be a 1 or 0 based on the contents of that section. This sometimes means a line might be divided into two sections in a way that the line isn't represented in the final binary matrix at all due to both sections not having enough of the line.

Figure 4: The pinboard simulation showing the binary matrix.

Finally, a pinboard simulation made in Godot shows the way the pinboard would represent the binary matrix. As visible, it is much easier to read this pinboard and understand what figure is being shown. Here, we have used colour coding to make it easier for us to visually see these differences, but in the final product, these pins would be raised and the tactile feedback should help visually impaired people perceive diagrams through the pinboard.

IV. COMPARATIVE STUDY

After having surveyed the internet and technical papers for similar solutions, we found a few devices that have a OCR based text to speech device. The primary problem with most of these devices is that they are not made in India and are far too expensive for the average person to afford. They all go above 1, 00, 000 INR. One of our core goals with this project is to make it affordable with minimal sacrifices to quality. We are collaborating with NGO to make sure we can get advice on how to keep the costs low while also providing all the features that might be necessary for a device like this.

Another important point to consider is that unlike the NIST system, our system is built to represent pins beyond the standard 6 pin layout and is scalable as such. It can go far beyond just a single character to be able to show multiple characters and even to display more complex figures like a square, circle, etc. The capabilities are limited only by the resolution of the pinboard but the system is equipped to go far beyond a basic braille system.

V. CONCLUSION

Since developing the hardware aspects of this project would require a lot of additional research and resources. Our goal would be to make a proof of concept prototype that could be expanded after completion of the project. The proof of concept we built has six pins, in line with the original braille system, however, we also built a simulator which helps understand the full scope of the project along with the algorithm to handle it. With proper funding and resources, the project has the potential to be a proper companion for blind people.

Development and implementation of an IoT-based educational companion for visually impaired individuals mark a significant step towards creating an inclusive and accessible learning environment. This innovative solution harnesses the power of technology to bridge the gaps that have traditionally hindered education for the visually impaired. By providing real-time access to information, interactive learning experiences, and personalized support, IoT devices empower visually impaired students to overcome challenges and engage with educational content effectively. Furthermore, the IoT-based educational companion not only enhances the learning experiences but also promotes independence and self-confidence among visually impaired individuals.

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